

A Study on Effect of Key Advertising Elements on Purchasing Behaviour of Consumers of Bhubaneswar, Odisha with Special Reference to Durable Goods

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Abstract

The present study aims to analyse the effect of selected advertising elements on purchasing behaviour of consumers towards durable products. The key advertising elements considered as independent variables include entertainment, advertising media, scepticism, cognition, and engagement. The consumer buying behaviour is considered as dependent variable. Consumers residing in Bhubaneswar city of Odisha were selected as the target respondents. Data were collected from 694 consumers through a structured questionnaire. Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) and regression analysis were employed for data analysis and interpretation. The results of the SEM analysis indicate that all advertising elements, except scepticism, have a positive relationship with consumer buying behaviour, whereas scepticism shows a negative relationship. Among the variables, engagement demonstrates the strongest impact with the highest beta coefficient. The findings suggest that advertising strategies emphasizing consumer engagement, informative content, and effective media placement are more likely to influence consumers' purchasing decisions for durable goods.

Keywords: *Advertising, Cognition, Durable Products, Engagement, Entertainment, Scepticism.*

INTRODUCTION

Advertising plays a crucial role in today's business environment by promoting products and services and driving consumer engagement. Over time, advertising strategies have changed, adapting to technological advances, changing consumer preferences, and broader societal shifts. One of its most powerful effects is building brand awareness; introducing new products and creating a distinct brand identity that helps them stand out in a crowded marketplace. Through repeated exposure and creative messaging, advertising boosts brand recognition, increasing the likelihood of consumer preference. Beyond visibility, it shapes consumer behaviour by appealing to emotions and fostering emotional bonds with brands (Kamran & Siddiqui, 2019; Kemp et al., 2012). Moreover, emotional appeals create trust and loyalty, strengthening the connection between consumers and brands. Furthermore, advertising shapes attitudes by influencing perceptions of product value and appeal (Kim & Sullivan, 2019). It serves as a vital source of information on product features, benefits, and pricing, enabling consumers to make informed decisions (Hoch & Ha, 1986). Moreover, advertising uses urgency tactics, such as limited-time offers, to prompt quick action. It also relies on social proof such as using testimonials, reviews, and popularity to sway buyers (Alenizi, 2023). Apart from this, by highlighting satisfied customers and strong demand, it builds trust and credibility. Given its multifaceted impact, advertising profoundly shapes consumer buying behaviour by altering preferences, attitudes, and decision-making. In this context, the present study

investigates key advertising elements that influence consumer purchasing behaviour, particularly for durable goods, which involve larger investments and longer decision timelines.

Importance of the study

Indeed, advertising plays a vital role in modern business by promoting products and generating consumer demand. In India, the expansion of the internet and digital technologies in the 21st century has significantly transformed advertising practices for durable goods. Businesses increasingly use online marketplaces, social media platforms, and search engines to target specific audiences, monitor consumer behaviour, and deliver personalized advertisements. E-commerce platforms such as Amazon and Flipkart provide detailed product information, customer reviews, and convenient shopping options that influence consumer decisions. Likewise, video-sharing platforms like YouTube allow brands to create engaging advertisements, often featuring celebrities or influencers to enhance credibility and attract younger audiences. The growing influence of social media personalities has further reshaped advertising through endorsements and product placements. In this context, the present study examines how key advertising factors influence consumers' purchasing decisions for durable goods.

Problem statement

Advertising is a key component of the marketing mix that promotes the sale of goods and services by creating awareness and interest among consumers. In today's media-rich environment, advertising reaches individuals through multiple channels such as television, radio, print, social media, and other digital platforms. Continuous exposure to these media significantly influences consumer behaviour by shaping their preferences, attitudes, and purchase decisions. Previous studies have emphasized the strong influence of advertising on consumer buying behaviour and have identified factors such as message content, media channels, cultural context, and consumer characteristics as important determinants. In this context, the present study examines the relationship between advertising and consumer behaviour by focusing on important elements such as consumer engagement, entertainment value, cognition, scepticism, and advertising media. Further, the study also examines the effect of key advertising elements on purchasing behaviour of consumers of durable goods in Bhubaneswar city, Odisha.

Research questions

Drawing from the problem statement, the following research questions have been formulated to be addressed through data analysis and interpretation:

- To what extent do different advertising media, ranging from traditional platforms to digital channels, influence consumers' decisions to purchase durable goods?
- How do advertising elements such as advertising media, consumer engagement, entertainment value, cognitive response, and price-quality scepticism influence consumer attitudes and subsequently affect their buying behaviour for durable goods?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Eminent researchers have carried out a good number of studies across the world to examine the relationship between advertising and consumer behaviour, particularly with regard to durable goods. The main findings of the recent such studies are presented below.

The studies conducted by Jakstiene et al. (2008), Dasar et al. (2013), Neethikumar and Aranganathan (2014), and Gupta and Singh (2022) reveal that consumer buying behaviour towards durable goods is greatly influenced by a combination of advertising, social, economic, and psychological factors. Amandeep et al. (2017) and Saravanakumar and Archana (2021) in their studies disclose the significant role of advertising in creating brand awareness, shaping consumer attitudes, and influencing purchase intentions. Further, advertising elements such as persuasiveness, attractiveness, media involvement, and information sources have been found to strongly affect consumers' decision-making processes. Rastogi and Chaudhary (2012), Adepoju and Joan (2015), Kumar and Kaushal (2019) and Sharma and Kaur (2020) carried out research studies where factors such as brand image, perceived quality, price consciousness, social influence, and demographic characteristics play a crucial role in determining consumer preferences for durable goods. The studies further emphasize that effective advertising strategies, along with an understanding of changing consumer lifestyles and values, are essential for marketers to enhance product adoption and sales. Jaiswal & Kant (2018), Higuera-Castillo et al. (2024) and Harisandi et al. (2025) in their research studies indicate the growing importance of sustainability-related advertising and green values in influencing purchase intentions for modern durable products such as electric vehicles and electric motorcycles. On the whole, these studies suggest that advertising remains a key determinant of consumer behaviour in the durable goods market, while highlighting the need for continuous research to better understand emerging consumer trends and advertising dynamics.

Objectives of the study

The primary objectives of the present research are:

- To examine the demographic profile of consumer respondents using selected durable products.
- To examine the impact of various advertising elements on consumer buying behaviour with reference to durable products.
- To provide practical recommendations for strengthening the positive influence of advertising elements on consumers' buying decisions with regard to durable goods.

Hypothesis of the study

The null hypothesis formulated for the present study is presented below which will be tested during the course of analysis.

H₀: There is no significant impact of advertising elements on consumer buying behaviour with respect to durable products.

Methodology of the study

The survey was conducted in Bhubaneswar city of Odisha to collect the primary data from the consumers who purchased and used durable products. Convenience sampling method was followed in collecting the primary data. For this purpose, a structured questionnaire was designed and a total of 694 consumer respondents were included in the final sample list. Thereafter, the reliability of the data set was tested using the Cronbach's Alpha test, which yielded a value of 0.67, indicating acceptable reliability of the data set and fit for the study. Statistical techniques such as structural equation modelling and regression analysis were applied for data analysis,

Development of the conceptual model

A conceptual model was developed to examine the influence of advertising elements on the purchasing behaviour of consumers with respect to durable products. The model includes five independent variables namely advertising media, entertainment, engagement, cognition, and scepticism representing key advertising elements and one dependent variable, i.e. consumer buying behaviour. This theoretical framework serves as the basis for the empirical investigation and is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Conceptual model showing effect of advertising on consumer buying behaviour

i) Analysis on demographic profile of consumer respondents

The demographic profile of the consumer respondents who participated in the survey was analysed using key variables such as gender, age, education, occupation, annual income, and family size.

Table 1: Demographic profile of consumer respondents (N=694)

Variables	No. of respondents	%
Gender:		
Male	409	58.9
Female	285	41.1
Age (in years):		
Below 25	71	10.2
25 to 35	271	39.0
36 to 45	262	37.8
Above 45	90	13.0
Education:		
Graduate	170	24.5
Post-graduate	212	30.5
Professional degree	232	33.4
Other higher degree	80	11.6
Occupation:		
Salaried	236	34.0
Self employed	191	27.5
Business	161	23.2
Others	106	15.3
Annual income (Rs. in lakh):		
Less than 3	200	28.8
3 to 5	136	19.6
5 to 10	172	24.8

Above 10	186	26.8
Family size: (in number)		
Up to 3	100	14.4
4	120	17.3
5	210	30.3
Above 5	264	38.0
Sources of information on durable product:		
Print media	196	28.2
Electronic media	279	40.2
Social media	142	20.5
Other source like friends/relatives	77	11.1

Source: Compiled from the survey data

Table-1 shows the distribution of the sample respondents based on their demographic characteristics. The table reveals that out of the total 694 respondents, 409 (58.9%) are male and 285 (41.1%) are female, indicating that the sample is largely dominated by male respondents. With regard to age, the highest proportion of respondents, 271 (39.0%), belong to the 25–35 years' age group, followed by 262 respondents (37.8%) in the 36–45 years' age group. In terms of educational qualification, 232 respondents (33.4%) possess professional qualifications, while 30.5% are postgraduates, indicating that a significant portion of the respondents are highly educated.

The occupational profile shows that 34.0% of the respondents are salaried employees, followed by 27.5% who are self-employed, suggesting that these two groups constitute the major share of the sample. Regarding annual income, 200 respondents (28.8%) fall in the income group of less than ₹3 lakhs, while 186 respondents (26.8%) belong to the above ₹10 lakhs category. Further, the table indicates that 264 respondents (38.0%) have a family size of more than five members, followed by 210 respondents who have five members in their family. Lastly, with respect to the source of information for purchase decisions, the majority of respondents, 279 (40.2%), rely on electronic media, while print media is the second most preferred source, accounting for 28.2%.

ii) Analysis on effect of advertising elements on consumer buying behaviour

To examine the impact of advertising elements on consumer buying behaviour, the study identified and analysed several key factors that influence advertising effectiveness. The research considered six major constructs: Engagement (ENG), Cognition (COG), Scepticism (SKEP), Entertainment (ENT), Advertising Media (ADMED), and Consumer Buying Behaviour (CBB). The analysis began with the application of factor analysis to determine the underlying structure and relative significance of these constructs. This step was undertaken to validate the dimensions and to ensure that the data were suitable for further statistical analysis. After validating the constructs through factor analysis, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was applied to examine and measure the relationships among them. SEM helped in providing a comprehensive understanding of how different advertising elements influence the consumer decision-making process in the purchase of durable products.

A) Factor analysis

To find the key factors and simplify the data set, factor analysis was applied using both Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). Six constructs namely ENT, ENG, SKEP, COG, ADMED (independent variables), and CBB (dependent variable) were analysed separately through EFA and CFA. Only those items with factor

loadings above 0.50 and acceptable communality values were retained within their respective constructs.

B) Structural Modelling Equation

After completing the EFA and CFA for the six constructs, the next step involved testing the structural model by incorporating all the latent variables. The structural model was developed using AMOS 20.0, and the results are presented in Fig. 2, which illustrates the path diagram of the structural equation model. The diagram depicts the relationships among the latent variables and their direct relationship on the dependent variable, i.e. consumer buying behaviour.

The coefficients presented in path diagram indicate that ENG (0.24), ADMED (0.15), and COG (0.11) have a positive relationship on CBB, whereas SKEP (-0.08) has a negative relationship on CBB. ENT (0.01) shows the weakest and statistically insignificant relationship with CBB. The regression weights presented in Table-2 further support these results. ENG ($\beta = 0.235$, CR = 4.797, $p < 0.05$), ADMED ($\beta = 0.113$, CR = 2.556, $p < 0.05$), and COG ($\beta = 0.101$, CR = 2.532, $p < 0.05$) exhibit significant positive effects on consumer buying behaviour. SKEP ($\beta = -0.081$, CR = -2.385, $p < 0.05$) also shows a statistically significant effect, but in a negative direction. However, ENT ($\beta = 0.011$, CR = 0.320, $p > 0.05$) does not show a statistically significant impact on consumer behaviour. Based on the p-values, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant impact of advertising elements on consumer buying behaviour with respect to durable products is rejected for all variables except entertainment. This indicates that most advertising elements significantly influence consumer buying behaviour.

Fig. 2: SEM path diagram with unstandardised estimates

Table 2: Summary of regression analysis

Variables	B	Std. β	S.E.	C.R.	P
CBB←ENG	0.235	0.273	0.049	4.797	0.000
CBB←COG	0.101	0.091	0.040	2.532	0.011
CBB←SKEP	-0.081	-0.080	0.034	-2.385	0.017
CBB←ENT	0.011	0.010	0.034	0.320	0.749
C CBB←ADMED	0.113	0.149	0.044	2.556	0.011

Table 3: Model fit summary for final structural model

Indices	Value
CMIN/DF	1.696
GFI	0.995
AGFI	0.983
NFI	0.974
TLI	0.972
CFI	0.989
PRATIO	0.400
RMSEA	0.032
AIC	40.179
BIC	108.316

Table-3 shows the model fit indices such as CMIN/DF, GFI, AGFI, NFI, TLI, PRATIO, and RMSEA, all of which fall within acceptable limits. These values indicate that the structural equation model adequately represents the relationships between advertising elements and consumer buying behaviour, thereby confirming a satisfactory model fit.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

The analysis of the demographic characteristics of the respondents indicates that male and female consumers constitute 58.9% and 41.1% of the sample, respectively. A majority of the respondents (39.0%) fall within the age group of 25–35 years. Further, 33.4% of the respondents possess professional degrees, indicating a relatively high level of education among the sample participants. In terms of occupation, 34.0% of the respondents belong to the salaried category. With respect to annual income, the largest group of respondents (200) falls within the income category of ₹3 lakh or less. Regarding family size, about 38.0% of the respondents have more than five members in their family. Finally, the sources of information for durable products reveal that the highest number of respondents (279) obtain information through electronic media.

The SEM analysis indicates that most advertising elements positively influence consumer buying behaviour, while scepticism shows a negative relationship. Among the variables, engagement demonstrates the strongest impact, as reflected by the highest beta coefficient. The p-values for engagement, cognition, scepticism, and advertising media are below 0.05, indicating that these relationships are statistically significant. However, entertainment is found to be statistically insignificant. These findings imply that advertising strategies emphasizing consumer engagement, informative content (cognition), and effective use of advertising media are more likely to influence the purchase decisions of durable goods. Overall, the study concludes that most advertising elements significantly shape consumer buying behaviour, except the entertainment factor.

Research contribution and managerial implications

This study contributes significantly to understanding the relationship between advertising and consumer buying behaviour. It underscores the importance of implementing well-planned advertising strategies to attract and retain consumers. The research also highlights the role of modern technology in improving advertising effectiveness and strengthening the relationship between brands and consumers. For managers, the findings offer practical insights into the advertising elements that have a significant influence on buying behaviour, thereby supporting more focused and effective campaign planning. Furthermore, the study provides a valuable

reference for future researchers and adds to the existing body of literature on advertising and consumer behaviour, particularly in the context of durable product marketing.

Limitation of the study and scope for future research

This study has certain limitations. The research was conducted with a limited sample and was restricted to respondents from Bhubaneswar city of Odisha; therefore, the findings may not fully represent the behaviour of a wider consumer population. Future researchers may consider expanding the sample by including respondents from different cities or regions. In addition, incorporating a broader range of durable products could further enhance the scope of the study. Future studies may also examine additional advertising-related variables to gain a deeper understanding of their influence on consumer buying behaviour. Such extensions would provide more comprehensive insights and improve the generalizability and relevance of the research findings.

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